

EVIDENCE COLLECTION SYSTEM FROM EVENT DATA RECORDER FOR CAR CRASH ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the effective way of retrieving data collected by event data recorder whenever accident occurred or crash detected. The Event Data Recorder (EDR) is one of the favorable solution for public safety. This event data recorder is composed of various sensors which are interfaced with processor for collecting vehicle status. This evidence collection system is nothing but the software based system which will collect data from EDR, process it and show the exact cause of accident. Graphical user interface (GUI) is constructed using Visual basic VB. NET software which shows readings of all sensors at the time of accident. This helps to design safer vehicles, driver behavior system, clear technical faults, issuing driving license, etc. This system can be implemented into any vehicle all over the world.

KEYWORDS: Event Data Recorder, Vehicle Monitoring, Evidence Collection system, crash analysis, police verification.

INTRODUCTION

Currently traditional method of crash analysis is being used in which cops need to visit accident site and check for signs of accident. Then they need to check for evidences like skid marks, degree of damage, collision part, eye witness etc. Often, there is situation of insufficient evidences. Sometimes it may also possible that some clues got missed by police. This is very time consuming and complex process. By using this evidence collection system we could perform analysis of accident cases just from police station. This reduces manpower, time and complexity over traditional system. Results obtained from analysis may also useful in driver training purpose, safety purpose, insurance issuing process etc. An Event Data Recorder is a device installed in vehicles to record information related to vehicle conditions crashes or accidents. Event Data Recorder is also commonly known as the "Black-Box". In recent time vehicles like trucks, cars etc. Black boxes are activated or triggered by the problems sensed by the electronic components like sensors. These problems also known as the electronically sensed Problems. Black Box preparedness to collect the statistically applicable crash information to enhance the safety of the vehicles. This collected information is stored micro SD memory card. This memory card is that much capable to store all data.

This system satisfies objectives which are, To build such an Evidence collection system which could construct clear picture of an accident, To design an Evidence collection system which will reduce time and complexity in police verification and accident analysis process, To provide sufficient memory space to store event data in form of micro SD memory storage card, To prevent falsification of data stored in memory card. There could be cases of data forgery or data modification and To construct such Evidence Collection System which helps in insurance cases.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE BLOCK DIAGRAM

Figure 1. Block Diagram of Evidence Collection System

As shown by block diagram, this system collects data from event data recorder and shows results using GUI. It's no more complexity. Just simple and convenient design is this.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
DATE	TIME	TEMPERATURE	DISTANCE	LONGITUDE	LATITUDE	SEAT BELT WORE	SPEED						
10-12-2014	10:10	37	1	37.764	78.897	YES	78 kmph						
10-12-2014	10:13	34	0.75	36.543	79.765	YES	112kmph						
10-12-2014	10:16	32	0.75	34.543	77.765	YES	111kmph						
10-12-2014	10:19	45	0.75	35.543	77.765	YES	102kmph						
10-12-2014	10:21	32	0.75	45.678	78.565	YES	90kmph						
10-12-2014	10:24	46	1	89.543	89.67	YES	88kmph						
10-12-2014	10:27	76	0.75	56.678	90.657	YES	92kmph						
10-12-2014	10:30	54	1	78.543	78.859	YES	45kmph						
10-12-2014	10:33	67	1	67.762	90.09	YES	29kmph						
10-12-2014	10:36	43	1	65.667	44.689	YES	65kmph						
10-12-2014	10:39	32	0.75	89.776	90.758	YES	92kmph						
10-12-2014	10:42	45	1	90.876	78.57	YES	93kmph						
10-12-2014	10:45	78	0.75	12.456	67.987	YES	72kmph						
10-12-2014	10:48	65	1	34.567	78.565	YES	52kmph						

Figure 2. Input data to be process by system

The above figure shows data stored in micro SD memory card. Parameters in this data are temperature, distance till front vehicle, latitude, longitude, seat belt status, speed of vehicle etc. Like this excel file is used to save whatever data collected by sensors.

B. FLOW CHART

Figure 3. Flow Chart of Evidence Collection System

As from block diagram, this system first fetches data from EDR. This is nothing but the recordings of various sensors while vehicle is running. Then Evidence Collection System processes this data. This data is organized in tabular form. Then we get outcomes such that comparison of Time Vs Speed, Time Vs steering angle, Time Vs

Temperature etc. After all this data processing, system tells exact cause/causes of accident. For that system checks threshold value of individual sensor. If a particular sensor has crossed threshold value, it's a cause of accident.

This system depends on continuously recording based EDR. This may need large amount of memory to store data. But, by using excel files this problem is solved. Then also we are using micro SD memory card of largest storage capacity to store this data. Data retrieval and analysis of recorded data is done through GUI which is prepared from Microsoft Visual Basic .Net (VB .NET). All information collected by sensors is shown by this GUI. This ECS system works at three interdependent levels.

Data Collection Level: At this level, data from different sensors are collected and stored in SD card. For this ARM processor is interfaced with all sensors. **Data Processing Level:** This is the main level where data from SD card is retrieved and processed. Various information required for post crash analysis is obtained here.

Human interference window: At this stage all processed data is made available for manual analysis. A separate GUI is constructed for this.

C. BREADTH FIRST SEARCH -TECHNIQUE

Now there is have huge data collected by all sensors. There must be a data mining algorithm which could handle this all data very effectively. That's why Breadth First Search technique is used here. This is most reliable search technique than any other.

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} A_{1,1} & \dots & A_{1,p_c} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{p_r,1} & \dots & A_{p_r,p_c} \end{pmatrix}$$

Figure 3. Data mining in Breadth First Search

As shown in figure, this technique maps data by row and column. Initially it selects first row. Then data on all columns of first row are mapped into system. Then again same technique for second row. Likewise all data of micro SD memory card is fetched into system. By this speed of system increases and dependability of system on external devices is reduced.

SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

A] MICROSOFT VISUAL BASIC:

VISUAL BASIC also known as VB is a high level programming language. It is evolved from the earlier programming language in the DOS version called as the BASIC. BASIC is the abbreviation for Beginner's All-purpose Symbolic Instruction Code. The Visual Basic programming codes resembles the English language. Different software companies generate the different versions of BASIC like Microsoft GWBASIC, QBASIC, QUICKBASIC, IBM BASICA and many more. It is easy programming language to learn and for anybody interested in programming but have a less knowledge of professional training in software engineering.

CONCLUSION

“Evidence Collection System from Event Data Recorder for Car Crash Analysis”, paper deals with results obtained from advanced Event Data Recorder for fault protection in vehicle to get data recorded. Also this paper aims to provide the actual cause of the accident or crash of the vehicle by retrieving the data from the EDR. Graphical comparison of various parameters such as speed, temperature, wheel rotations etc. with respect to time is also done. Time wise analysis of particular sensor is much easier due to these results. These results are also helpful in cases like Driver training program, Insurance cases, Police verification etc.

REFERENCES

- [1] Shital V.Vaidya, Prof.P.H.Chandankhede, “Designing of Event Data Recorder for Vehicle Monitoring based on ARM processor” International Conference Emerging Trends in Science, Engineering, Business and Disaster Management ICBDM 2014 , Image Processing and Networking Volume:8 Special Issue IV, Feb 2014, ISSN No:0973-2993.
- [2] Nitin P. Sirsikar,Prof. Pankaj H. Chandankhede,“ Design of ARM based Enhanced Event Data Recorder & Evidence Collecting System”, IOSR Journal of Electronics and Communication Engineering (IOSRJECE) e-ISSN: 2278-2834,p-ISSN: 2278-8735.Volume 9, Issue 5, Ver. V (Sep -Oct. 2014), PP 23-29.
- [3] Monisha J Prasad, Arundathi S, Nayana Anil, Kariyappa B. S., “Automobile Black Box System For Accident Analysis”, International Conference On Advances In Electronics, Computers and Communications (ICAECC) 2014.
- [4] Pravin kumar, V. Anuragh, NLP Raju, “Accelerometer Based Vehicle Monitoring And Tracking System Using ARM Processor And GPS”, International Journal of Science Engineering and Advance Technology, IJSEAT, Volume 2, Issue 11, ISSN 2321-6905 November-2014.
- [5] Anoop Mathew, Joseph Kuncheria, Yadukrishnan S, Gifty Raju, Haritha Chandrasekhar, “Car Black Box”, International Journal of Innovative Science and Modern Engineering (IJISME) ISSN: 2319-6386, Volume-2 Issue-11, October 2014
- [6] Kangsuk Chae, Daihoon Kim, Seohyun Jung, Jaeduck Choi, and Souhwan Jung ,”Evidence Collecting System fromCar Black Boxes”, School of Electronics Engineering, Soongshil University Seoul,Korea 2013.
- [7] Mooseop Kim and Chi Yoon Jeong, “An Efficient Data Integrity Scheme for Preventing Falsification of Car Black Box”,ICTC pp. 1020-1021, 2013.
- [8] Scott Beamer, Aydın Buluc, Krste Asanovi´c David Patterson, “Distributed memory Breadth First Search Revisited: Enabling Bottom Up Search”, 2013 IEEE 27th International Symposium on Parallel & Distributed Processing Workshops.
- [9] P. Ajay Kumar Reddy, P.Dileep Kumar, K. Bhaskar reddy, E.Venkataramana, M.Chandra sekhar Reddy, “Black box for vehicles”, IJEI Volume 1, issue 7, October 2012, pp 06-12.
- [10] Abdallah Kassem, Rabih Jabr, Ghady Salamouni, Ziad Khairallah Maalouf, ” Vehicle Black Box System”, IEEE International Systems Conference Montreal, Canada, April 7-10, 2008.
- [11] Artis Mednis y, Atis Elsts y, Leo Selavo y, “Embedded Solution for Road Condition Monitoring Using Vehicular Sensor Networks”, IEEE ,2012.L
- [12] Chulhwa Hong, Truong Le, Kangsuk Chae, and Souhwan Jung, “Evidence Collection from Car Black Boxes using Smartphone’s” , The 8th Annual IEEE Consumer Communications and Networking Conference – Demos,2011.